

Temple of the Jedi Order

also known as “International Church of Jediism”

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**Supervised Entry, prepared from a literature review by a student or students under the direction of a Supervisor, typically as a classroom project; edited and vetted by Supervisor.*

Entry tags: New Religious Movement (NRM), New Religious Movement, Transnational Cybersect, Religious Group

Jediism is a religion that uses the term 'Jedi' from the Star Wars universe created by George Lucas. Members of the Temple of the Jedi Order refer to themselves as Jedis and base their religion in 'The Force.' The Force is defined as a "a ubiquitous and metaphysical power...the underlying, fundamental nature of the universe," by leadership within the Temple of the Jedi Order. Please note that The Temple of the Jedi Order is NOT affiliated with or worshipping George Lucas and his creations.
<https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/>

Date Range: 2007 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Internet Based

Region tags: Global, Cybersect

This religion is housed on the internet with no temples or regions of importance.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: The Myth Awakens

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/doctrine-of-the-order>

– Source 1 Description: Doctrine of the Temple of the Jedi Order

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The library listed online for members of the Temple of the Jedi Order contains texts from a variety of other religions. Jedes are often seen referencing these texts to support their own religious beliefs.

Reference: . Library - Temple of the Jedi Order.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: General process for becoming a registered Jedi is to simply fill out a page on their website.

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: As of now this religion is extremely young and has yet to see any prolific increase in members based on births to current members. In coming years we could see this change, however it is doubtful as much of the religious group is based on personal choice.

Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Being a young religion, people must convert to or join. There is no established measures for a way to join other than by choice and there are no barriers on who can elect to become a Jedi.

Assigned by class:

– No

Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Assigned by gender:

– No

Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: There are 3 factors one must meet to become a member "A belief in the Force. The Force resides within you, surrounds you and flows through you. Acceptance of our teachings and Doctrine. These serve as spiritual guidance for Jedi. You may hold other spiritual

convictions along with being a Jedi. A completed Membership Application." (From <https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/faq#HowtoJoin>)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: There is no official mission by the Temple to recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: No political support in the sense of a political group actively campaigning along side the temple or contributing to their existence, instead multiple governmental agencies (thus political entities) have

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16474

Notes: This is the number of registered users on the Temple of the Jedi Order website. It is not reported the number of active vs inactive users. (<https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/community/users>)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The doctrine listed online includes: Jedi Believe The Three Tenets The Code The Creed The 16 Teachings The 21 Maxims (<https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/doctrine-of-the-order>)

Reference: Temple of the Jedi Order

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Can be found here <https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/doctrine-of-the-order>

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: While many think this is based on "Star Wars," the story of the films has no importance in Jediism. When looking online at the doctrine and FAQ page of website a story cannot be found

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Internet based with no physical structure or representation

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Internet based with no physical structure or representation

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Notes: Only icon/symbol in the religion is the attached file here. Meaning is as follows: 1. The Jedi Code (5 star) 2. The 16 Teachings (inner 16 star) 3. The interdependence of Light and Dark.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Belief in "The Force," a metaphysical thing that exists in and around all that is living. The force will continue in death

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Not reincarnation in the traditional sense, but there is a belief that one's "force" goes back into the world after death

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: In general there are no special rites or practices surrounding the death of a Jedi

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Force is the supernatural being. It is defined as, "a ubiquitous and metaphysical power that a Jedi (a follower of Jediism) believes to be the underlying, fundamental nature of the universe." As found in the doctrine of the order (<https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/doctrine-of-the-order>)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Force is the supreme high god, in fact it is the only thing that can be considered superhuman/godly

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The Force has no physical manifestation.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

Notes: Supreme high god is not entirely a god and is instead a part of the universe, the most important and influential piece of the universe

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Force is essentially the driving force behind all that happens in the world

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The casual efficacy held by The Force is not deliberate, the force will act on the universe when there is not balance.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: When the universe is not in balance the Force will respond. The universe is ever changing and fluid, Jedis are taught to "live in and focus on the Now. We let ourselves

flow like water through the events around us. We embrace the ever changing and fluid world, adapting and changing as it does." (From the 16 Teachings, teaching 4 <https://www.templeofthejediorder.org/doctrine-of-the-order>)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Notes: No emotion is expressed

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

Notes: No emotion is expressed

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: It is not a god in the traditional sense, it is the supreme high power within the universe. Unseen, but felt by all

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Human's all have the force within them, after death the force leaves the body and returns to the larger force that inhabits all living and nonliving objects. There are no spirits in the traditional sense, like ghosts.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The force is this non-human supernatural being

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The force doesn't make decisions, it does not cause anything to happen in a deliberate way. Things are impacted by the force when there is not balance of good and bad in the world

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Only the Force is present

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: The Force can sense unbalance, it responds to that. Unbalance in the universe as a whole

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Each Jedi is capable of impacting the force and those around them.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Some Jedi will wear robes during times of prayer

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Name changes are seen on occasion by devout followers

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: In general english is used

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Temple of the Jedi Order

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Temple of the Jedi Order

Reference: . Library - Temple of the Jedi Order.